

What is Life

Atoms, molecules and cells

Key ideas:

- living things are made up of non-living matter called atoms
- cells are the smallest thing that we can say is 'alive'
- some living things are made up of only a single cell. Others are made up of many cells working together
- plant cells and animal cells are different.

All things in the universe, including living things, are made up of tiny particles called atoms. A collection of atoms bound together to act as a single unit is called a molecule. (In the image above, different coloured atoms are connected together to form a molecule.)

Some molecules (such as water molecules and sugar molecules) contain just a few atoms. Other molecules, such as protein and enzyme molecules, contain thousands of atoms. Other molecules, such as DNA strands, contain millions of atoms.

Cells are made up of molecules. All living things are made up of cells. While cells are alive, molecules and atoms are not.

Single-celled organisms are described as 'microscopic', as the individual cells can only be seen by using a microscope. Examples of this kind of organism include yeasts, bacteria, protozoa and algae. However, some of these examples can exist as a colony of many cells. We can sometimes see a colony with our own eyes (for example, seeing mould growing on cheese).

Multi-celled organisms are described as 'macroscopic', and are easily seen with the human eye. Examples of macroscopic organisms include animals, trees and grasses. These organisms have cells that operate in different ways; the cells specialise for certain functions but collaborate for the well-being of the whole organism. For example, in humans, red blood cells carry oxygen to different parts of the body. White blood cells fight infection, kidney cells filter out impurities in the blood stream, fat cells store energy for the long term, and so on. Stem cells are special because they can adapt to one of the other specialisations.

Plant and animal cells look a lot alike. However, plant cells have some unique features like rigid cell walls and special organelles (little organs) for photosynthesis.

Activity: More about atoms and molecules

Read:

[What are Bacteria?](#) Some easy reading from the Children's University of Manchester.

[Plant & Animal Cells Staining Lab](#) This laboratory exercise includes images taken under a light microscope.

[Cells to systems – Animal cells and plant](#) This BBC site includes simple diagrams and a table which highlights the main distinctions between animal and plant cells.

[Single GFP-Expressing Cell Is Basis of Living Laser](#) In this Science Daily article, science seems to meet science fiction as scientist create lasers out of living cells.

[Science still the key to our](#) The Dominion Post reports an example of New Zealand stem cell research making a difference.

Your text book describes more about the differences and similarities between plant and animal cells.

View:

[Bill Nye's atoms and molecules](#) (watch the first 8 minutes)

[Learn Biology: Cells – cell theory.](#) (2 minutes.) _____

[White Blood Cell Chases Bacteria –](#) (30 seconds.)

[Protozoa.](#) (5 minutes.) A video about pond water life.

[You are mostly](#) What does it mean to be human if our body cells are outnumbered by the microbes on and in us? (4 minutes)

Do:

[Cell Size and](#) An activity to illustrate the size of cells and their parts. Click on the slider below the diagram to zoom in and out.

[Animal and Plant](#) An activity to teach you about key parts of the cell.

You might like to try [I wonder about cells?](#) (pdf 183 KB), as an example of working like a scientist.

Caution: DO NOT attempt to grow bacterial cultures. This is a hazardous activity requiring stringent health and safety precautions, and we would really like you to stay safe. (Research in New Zealand schools indicates the majority of schools fail to meet health and safety guidelines when they attempt such activities, and we really can't expect the average home to be much better.)